

A DESCRIPTIVE STUDY TO ASSESS THE AWARENESS ON IMPORTANCE OF ANTENATAL EXERCISE AMONG ANTENATAL MOTHERS IN SELECTED TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL, KELAMBAKKAM, KANCHIPURAM DISTRICT, TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

A descriptive study to assess the mother's knowledge on antenatal exercise. The research setting in study was conducted at the Obstetrical and Gynecological outpatient department, Chettinad Hospital and Research Institute, Kancheepuram district, Tamilnadu, India. The sample participation was voluntary 30 samples was used in the study. Data was collected for the period of 1 week, research tool was structured interview schedule to assess the demographic profile of the sample and structured questionnaire to assess the mother's knowledge on antenatal exercise, inadequate knowledge level of frequency was 28 and percentage is 47%, moderate knowledge level of frequency was 2 and percentage is 53%, adequate knowledge level of frequency and percentage was 0%,

Key Words: Mothers, Knowledge & Antenatal Exercise

Introduction:

Exercise naturally makes to feel good both mentally and physically. Exercising increases the production of serotonin which makes to feel better emotionally. The more care we take of our bodies means the better they function and this includes during pregnancy and birth. There have been plenty of studies conducted that show that gentle exercising in pregnancy leads to an easier pregnancy and less complications during labour. Pregnancy is a good time to develop healthy lifestyle habit including regular exercise and good nutrition. During pregnancy there are several forms of "safe exercises" such as: yoga which can be done after 12th week of pregnancy, Pilates, walking its free and get the added bonus of sunlight and fresh air which are great mood boosters, swimming and aqua natal classes (aqua natal after 16 weeks). Exercise during pregnancy is usually beneficial depending on the woman's state of health conditioning and stage of pregnancy. Exercise provides a diversion reduces anxiety and tension quiets the mind promotes sleep helps to decrease constipation and stimulates the appetite all of which are valuable aids to the pregnant women. Specific exercise & posture can be helping the pregnant women to adopt the physical changes her body during the child bearing age. They are as follows: abdominal tightening, pelvic rocking, pelvic floor exercises, Foot & leg exercises, sit or half lie with legs supported, breathing awareness, and client education.

James Clapp (2008) stated that most pregnant women restrict their mobility and their participation in routine activities, but studies have proved that daily exercise can reduce chance of miscarriage by 40%. 1, 2 United states researchers have observed that moderate exercises such as walking / cycling can prevent pregnancy induced hypertension(PIH).Exercise can also prevent early onset of labour, premature rupture of membrane and can help to shorten the duration of labour. Exercise helps mother to loose pregnancy weight faster, it decreases aches and pain associated with pregnancy. The general benefits of aerobic exercise for pregnant women include reducing blood pressure decreases cardiac-vascular such as clot formation, helping to maintain ideal body weight and managing stable diabetes. Pregnant women who exercise have generally shorter labour and faster, easier deliveries.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To assess the awareness on importance of antenatal exercise.
- ✓ To associate the awareness on importance of antenatal exercise with selected demographic and obstetrical variables.

Methodology:

The researchers are used descriptive research design using a quantitative approach.

Sample: 30 antenatal mothers in a selected hospital .who were selected by using convenience sample technique.

Tool Used: Self administered questionnaire.

Statistical Technique Used: Descriptive statistics used to analyze the data.

Finding and Discussion:

Table 1: Distribution of Frequency and percentage of structured questionnaires of antenatal mothers

S.No	Level of Variables	Frequency (N=30)	Percentage (%)
1	Inadequate	28	47%
2	Moderate	2	53%
3	Adequate	0	0%

Table 1 shows that 47% of antenatal mothers had inadequate knowledge whereas 0% of adequate knowledge.

Table 2: Association of demographic variables and the level of knowledge

S.No	Demographic Variable	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)	CHI ² (X ²)	p Value
1	Age	12	40%	5.0	12.59 *
	a)20-25 years	11	37%		
	b)26-30 years	7	23%		
	c)31-35 years	0	0%		
	d)>35 years				
2	Religion	19	63%	11.82	12.59 *
	a)Hindu	8	27%		
	b)Christian	2	7%		
	c)Muslim	1	3%		
	d)Others				
3	Educational Status	6	20%	16.2	12.59 *
	a)primary	7	23%		
	b)secondary	17	57%		
	c)graduate	0	0%		
	d)illiterate				
4	Family Income	2	7%	21.75	12.59 *
	a)<5000	10	33%		
	b)5000-10000	7	23%		
	c)10000-20000	11	37%		
	d)>20000				
5	Occupation	2	7%	72.35	12.59 *
	a)sedentary workers	16	53%		
	b)moderate workers	1	3%		
	c)heavy workers	11	37%		
	d)un employment				
6	Type of Family	10	33%	1.04	9.49 NS
	a)joint family	20	67%		
	b)nuclear family	0	0%		
	c)extended family				
7	Source of Information	11	37%	67.6	12.59 *
	a)health professionals	6	20%		
	b)relatives and friends	6	20%		
	c)internet	7	23%		
	d)others				

Table 2: Shows that the antenatal exercise knowledge of antenatal mothers was significant associated with the demographic variables such as age, religion, educational status, family income, occupation.

Conclusion:

This study helps us to understand that the need of awareness on importance of antenatal exercise among antenatal mothers.

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